

Cultivation of Rhubarb in Alley Cropping Tree Tows

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(AGFORWARD)
Apples and rhubarb at Tolhurst Organics Agroforestry, UK

In agroforestry systems, the space between and beneath tree canopies remains underutilized and can lead to challenges in weed control. However, this area can be transformed into a productive zone by cultivating crops that are adapted to low light conditions. *Rhubarb*, a hardy under story crop, can thrive in the shaded environment of tree rows and can be harvested and processed alongside other farm produce. Integrating crops like *rhubarb* into the tree under story optimizes land use, enhancing farm productivity, particularly in the early years when tree rows are not yet fully productive. This practice helps mitigate the loss of land that would otherwise be taken out of direct crop production, ensuring the farm remains more productive during the tree establishment phase. *Rhubarb* stands out not only for its ability to thrive in shaded conditions but also for its minimal management requirements once established. As a perennial vegetable, it has a long cultivation period of approximately 9 years. Its role in the under story also aids in weed control. Moreover, the active management of the under story contributes to increased biodiversity on the farm and enhancing pollinator populations. While harvesting crops in tree rows can be challenging with machinery, *rhubarb's* manual harvesting process makes it ideal for this environment. The harvesting period for rhubarb typically occurs from May to July, offering a seasonal window for production. *Rhubarb* can be processed into various products, including compotes, jams, and sauces, or sold fresh or frozen. This creates opportunities for short-chain sales, diversifying the farm's income streams. The inclusion of rhubarb as an under story crop helps offset the implementation costs of alley cropping systems and provides income during the period before the tree rows become fully productive. Through the integration of under story crops like rhubarb, agroforestry systems can maximize land use, increase farm resilience, and contribute to a more sustainable agricultural model.

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